

IMPORTANT TASKS OF TEACHING LATIN IN MEDICAL SCHOOLS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the use of new pedagogical technologies in the program of Latin language course. The existing methods of teaching Latin in medical universities are analyzed. The need to use innovative approaches in teaching, including computer teaching, distance education, extracurricular education through teaching using interactive methods was identified and justified. The need to revise the current education system in favor of a professionally oriented, socio-cultural approach was emphasized. The urgent task of developing students' linguistic abilities is the development of intensive forms of education.*

Keywords: *communicative competence, comparative method, Latin language, thermocouples, vocabulary, interdisciplinary teaching methods, analytical activity.*

Introduction: In the past, Latin was considered one of the oldest subjects in higher education, as well as one of the academic subjects in secondary school. For this reason, the teaching methods are predominantly conservative, and the teaching methods are one of the methods used for a long time. That is, the teaching system of these methods is quite outdated. It is recommended to continue to work on the issue of using modern methods of teaching Latin in medical, scientific and legal educational institutions. Therefore, it is appropriate to use various interactive methods during the lesson to make it more understandable.

The study of Latin has a purely professional purpose - to prepare a terminologically competent doctor. Vocabulary is one of the most important components of Latin lessons. A Latin dictionary that will help to work with medical terminology in the future. In addition to medical terminology, Latin aphorisms are also used in lessons, knowledge of which helps students not only recognize centuries-old wisdom, but also better remember Latin words. The main point of theoretical and practical research on the intensification of teaching foreign languages, especially Latin, is called the method of conscious comparison. The essence of this method is that at certain stages of the development of methodological and linguistic thought of students, the comparison of the native and foreign languages from a methodological and linguistic point of view is not only effectively linked, but also stimulates each other. At the same time, the native language is the basis of the conscious-comparative teaching method.

Among all the subjects taught in higher medical schools, Latin is of particular importance. Since Latin is not included in the list of foreign languages in medical universities, it is a separate department of normal and topographic human anatomy, and in this regard, the science of Latin occupies a special place among physiology and anatomical sciences.

The methodology of teaching Latin is clear and, unlike the methodology of teaching the humanities, teaching this subject requires a special approach, because no one speaks this language today. First of all, it is necessary to talk about how to interest students in this subject, day after day discover new features of this subject, taking an important place in their future profession. In this case, the orthographically correct spelling of each part of the face comes first.

One of the urgent tasks of developing students' language abilities is the development of intensive forms of training. The main point of theoretical and practical research on the intensification of teaching foreign languages and Latin is the method of conscious comparison. The essence of this method is that at certain stages of students' linguistic thinking, the comparison of their native and foreign languages in the methodological language plan not only effectively connects, but also stimulates each other. At the same time, the native language is the basis of the conscious-comparative teaching method.

In the learning process, the teacher's task is to develop methods for using English as an assistant, and not as an interfering enemy. The Latin teachers of the Higher Medical School have extensive experience working with foreign students learning Latin through Russian as an intermediary. It is quite another thing to teach Latin to an English-speaking audience without an intermediary language. In English- and Romance-speaking countries, doctors write international terms in Latin, ignoring only the norms of Latin grammar. English is based on Latin, so foreign students can easily learn the vocabulary. Studying Latin in medical school involves learning vocabulary, grammar, terminological elements. One of the current tasks of developing students' language abilities is the development of intensive forms of training. Students will be familiar with the basics of medical terminology in order to successfully continue their studies in the field of medicine. The purpose of the Latin teaching method is to explain to students in an understandable, simple language in combination with other subjects: for example, Russian, English and French, anatomy, physiology, taught in medical universities.

Conclusion. An integral part of the professional competence of a future doctor is the ability to know and use medical terminology. Terminological competence is formed in Latin classes, which are part of the integrated educational process of future doctors. Teaching Latin as a foreign language has a long history, dating back more than fifteen centuries, and certainly deserves detailed study. The main objective of the subject "Medical Terminology" at the Faculty of Medicine is to help students understand medical terms as much as possible, understand the term itself and the structure of its components, quickly and correctly write prescriptions, recognize the names of medicines, and place stresses.

To sum up, we can say that the main goal of Latin language teaching methodology is to develop students' professional competence in medical terminology, master the basics of Latin language, which will allow them to read, write and translate correctly, and the text will also allow them to explain the essence.

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